

PRACTICE OF DEVELOPING INTERCULTURAL COMPETENCE OF FUTURE FOREIGN LANGUAGE TEACHERS IN UNIVERSITIES

Mirzayeva Sayyora Rustamjon qizi

doctoral student of Namangan State University

Email: ermamatova.sayyora94@gmail.com

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16880807>

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada biz talabalarning chet tilini o'rganishdagi madaniyatlararo kompetensiyasi, mavzuga oid ba'zi masalalar va dars davomida muvaffaqiyatga erishish yo'llari haqida gapirishni maqsad qilganmiz. "Asl dunyo" va "maqsadli jamoa olami" o'rtasidagi munosabatni bilish, bilish va tushunish (o'xshashlik va farqli farqlar) madaniyatlararo ongni keltirib chiqaradi.

Kalit so'zlar: Madaniy jihatlar, madaniyatlararo kompetentsiya, madaniy o'ziga xosliklar, madaniyatlararo uchrashuvlar.

Аннотация: В данной статье мы рассмотрим межкультурную компетентность студентов, изучающих иностранный язык, некоторые вопросы, связанные с этой темой, и пути достижения успеха на занятиях. Знание, осознание и понимание взаимосвязи (сходств и отличительных различий) между «исходным миром» и «миром целевого сообщества» формируют межкультурную компетентность.

Ключевые слова: Культурные аспекты, межкультурная компетентность, культурная идентичность, межкультурные контакты.

Abstract: In this article we aim to speak about intercultural competence of students` in learning a foreign language, some issues relating the theme and ways of achieving success during the class. Knowledge, awareness and understanding of the relation (similarities and distinctive differences) between the 'world of origin' and the 'world of the target community' produce an intercultural awareness.

Keywords: Cultural aspects, intercultural competence, cultural identities, intercultural encounters.

There has been an increase in the importance of the cultural aspect in teaching and learning foreign languages, and teachers nowadays are supposed to stimulate the acquisition and development of intercultural competence in their students. Foreign language teaching and learning should be regarded from an intercultural perspective. The foreign language classes can be the link between the two cultures by which students have the opportunity to discover other values, mentalities, and facets of life. In doing this, a new vision should be taken into consideration, in which the teacher naturally and harmoniously

combines the linguistic and cultural elements in the educational process during all types of lessons, irrespective of the topic being dealt with, or whether they focus on grammar or vocabulary issues. The culture and civilization notions must not be regarded separately, but should be integrated in the activities meant to develop the four language skills.

There are many ways in which modern languages are currently learnt and taught. Cultural identities (the identities which people construct on the basis of their membership of cultural groups) are a particular type of social identity. Culture itself is a notoriously difficult term to define. Cultures also change over time because of their members' internal contestation of the meanings, norms, values and practices of the group. The ways in which individuals relate to the cultures to which they are affiliated are complex. Because cultural participation and cultural practices are context-dependent and variable, individuals use the multiple cultural resources which are available to them in a fluid manner to actively construct and negotiate their own meanings and interpretations of the world across the various contexts which they encounter in their everyday lives. However, cultures also constrain and limit the thoughts and actions of individuals. Cultural affiliations influence not only how people perceive themselves and their own identities, but also how they perceive others, other groups and other ways of acting, thinking and feeling, and how they perceive the relationships between groups. Intercultural competence is therefore a combination of attitudes, knowledge, understanding and skills applied through action which enables one, either singly or together with others, to: -- understand and respect people who are perceived to have different cultural affiliations from oneself; -- respond appropriately, effectively and respectfully when interacting and communicating with such people; -- establish positive and constructive relationships with such people; -- understand oneself and one's own multiple cultural affiliations through encounters with cultural "difference".

Here, the term "respect" means that one has regard for, appreciates and values the other; the term "appropriate" means that all participants in the situation are equally satisfied that the interaction occurs within expected cultural norms; and "effective" means that all involved are able to achieve their objectives in the interaction, at least in part.

Intercultural competence involves an awareness of the role of language competences in intercultural encounters. It also involves an awareness that, within intercultural encounters (as in all interactions), participants may have different levels of competence in the language(s) being used, which can create

asymmetries or power differentials within the interaction. More generally, how people interpret, and communicate within, intercultural encounters is shaped by the languages and cultures which they bring to those encounters.

Intercultural encounters have now become an everyday occurrence for large numbers of people in many countries. Such high levels of physical and virtual intercultural contact have the potential to lead to self-enrichment and benefit, since encountering otherness, or what is perceived to be different, provides an opportunity for learning from, with and about each other and about oneself. Developing intercultural competence through education is a powerful tool for achieving intercultural understanding, appreciation and respect. The successful development of intercultural competence, and the realisation of the social vision upon which it is based, relies crucially upon the commitment and support of a wide range of stakeholders, including politicians, policy makers, education and training professionals, religious, spiritual and community leaders, parents and carers, and of course learners themselves. To enable the development of intercultural competence through education, the committed support of all these stakeholders is required.

References

1. Bell, R., Lederman, N. & Abd-El-Khalick, F. (2000) Developing and acting upon one's conception of the nature of science: a follow-up study, *Journal of Research in Science Teaching*, 37, 563–581.
2. Borg, S. (1998) Teachers' pedagogical systems and grammar teaching: a qualitative study, *TESOL Quarterly*, 32, 9–38.
3. Mirzaeva S. R. "Technologies for Developing Intercultural Competence of Future Foreign Language Teachers Through Reading Literary Works (on The Example of Methods of Reading the Work of Immigrant-Muslim Writers in the USA)", *Journal of Higher Education and Academic Advancement e-ISSN : 3032-1123 JHEAA*, Vol. 2, No. 3, March 2025 Page 214-216
4. Mirzaeva S. R., Sadikov Z. Ya. "CONSISTENCY IS THE MAIN REQUIREMENT OF THE PSYCHOLOGY OF TEACHING A FOREIGN LANGUAGE", *AMERICAN International Scientific Online Conference: «ACADEMIC RESEARCH IN MODERN SCIENCE» A collection of articles by Central Asian scholars Issue 37, Part 2, October 10, 2024*
5. Byram, M. (1997) *Teaching and assessing intercultural communicative competence* (Clevedon, Multilingual Matters).

